

THE JOURNAL
OF THE
BOMBAY BRANCH
OF THE
ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY.

EXTRA NUMBER.

THE CENTENARY MEMORIAL VOLUME.

(Edited by the Honorary Secretary.)

BOMBAY :

SOCIETY'S LIBRARY, TOWN HALL.

LONDON :

KEGAN PAUL, TRENCH, TRÜBNER & Co.,
DRYDEN HOUSE, 43, GERARD ST., SOHO, W. C.

1905.

3.—*On the Search for Sanskrit Manuscripts in the Bombay Circle.*

BY PROF. S. R. BHANDARKAR, M.A.

TOWARDS the end of October 1903, I was packed off suddenly, without any previous intimation whatsoever, to Central India and Rajputana, being deputed "on special duty to make a preliminary tour" through those and the Central Provinces "with a view to enable me to report what further operations are required for the thorough investigation of, and the cataloguing of, the Sanskrit manuscripts in the Bhând&rs in those provinces." It came about in this way. The Agent to the Governor-General, Central India, had some months previously suggested to the Government of India that it was desirable that steps should be taken to catalogue the Sanskrit manuscripts in Central India, large numbers of which are believed to exist in that Agency, both in private libraries and in temple records. This matter was referred to my colleague, Prof. Pathak, and myself, as Central India, Rajputana and the Central Provinces were attached to the Bombay Circle when the total grant for the search for Sanskrit manuscripts was re-distributed by the Government of India in 1879. As a result of our reports I was ordered to make the preliminary tour referred to. It was to be a tour of three months, and I returned towards the end of January of last year, doing within that period as many places as it was possible for me to do. The report I made of my tour was printed, and at my request copies were distributed to certain scholars and public institutions. In forwarding the report to Government the head of my department recommended that I should be sent on a year's tour again from the beginning of the present year.

It was at this stage that our Secretary appealed to me for a paper on the present occasion. I mentioned to him the tour I had made and the tour on which I expected to be sent again and said that it was unfortunately not likely that I should be in Bombay to witness the present celebration. This, instead of making him give me over, put into his mind the idea of proposing that I should write something in connection with the search for Sanskrit manuscripts and though I did not then definitely agree to the proposal I found my name put in the tentative programme. After that I did not like to refuse.

Looking with a natural curiosity into the published account of a similar celebration by our sister institution on the Bengal side,

I found mention made of a creditable amount of work done both as regards the publication of Sanskrit works and the search for Sanskrit manuscripts. In connection with the latter the Bengal Asiatic Society purchased a large number of manuscripts and also issued catalogues of private libraries of manuscripts "in order to bring to light the treasures of Sanskrit-lore buried in those libraries." The catalogues published and called "Notices of Sanskrit MSS." do not merely give the names of the works and of the authors and the numbers of leaves, &c., but give other information besides, especially abstracts of contents. Aufrecht has praised them very highly. It is not, however, by means of its own funds that the Society has been able to do the work both of the publication of texts and of the search for manuscripts, but by means of funds set apart by Government for that purpose and placed at the disposal of the Society. Work corresponding to it has on this side been done by Government direct through its Educational Department and its own Educational Officers. It might, therefore, be thought that the subject of the search for Sanskrit manuscripts would have no more intimate connection with the Bombay Asiatic Society than that of a scientific interest merely. Yet the Society has done what little it could in this line also. It published as an extra No. of its Journal Dr. Bühler's detailed report of a tour in search for Sanskrit manuscripts made in Kaśmir, Rajputana and Central India, which report Dr. Aufrecht calls "a publication of great importance." Later, Dr. Peterson's reports on the search for the years 1882-83, 1883-84, 1884-86, and 1886-92 were also published as extra Nos. of the Journal. The Society has, moreover, got a small collection of manuscripts presented to it, of a part of which a list has been recently issued.

It would not be out of place here to mention a few of the most important points in the reports just referred to as having been published under the auspices of the Society.

Dr. Bühler's Kaśmir report is replete with information. There is in it an interesting account of the Brahmans of that province and of the manuscripts seen there. The account given of some of the manuscripts acquired there for Government includes valuable information about certain poets and their works, such as Ratnākara, Kshemendra, Bilhana, Mañkha and the Rājatarāṅginî, and about the literature relating to Alamkāra and the Spanda and Pratyabhijñā shastras. The report further contains a few notes on the Kaśmīrī language also. The list of manuscripts purchased is accompanied by copious extracts from some of them.

In Dr. Peterson's reports also many interesting finds are reported and many works and authors, Jaina as well as Brāhmaṇa, are noticed. The value of the reports is further enhanced by very useful and

important appendices. In addition to the lists of manuscripts purchased for Government and copious extracts from them, the appendices contain the following :—

Extracts from manuscripts belonging to their Highnesses the Maharajahs of Udaipur and Ulwar, and from books preserved in libraries at Ahmedabad, Boondi, Kotah, Indore and Cambay.

Catalogue of the palm-leaf manuscripts in the Śāntināth Bhāndār, Cambay.

An Index of Books to the first three reports, which, however, does not include the manuscripts purchased for Government.

A very helpful Index of Authors “in which an endeavour has been made to present in a form convenient for reference all the information about the various writers gleaned from the extracts furnished with the first three reports,” supplemented, wherever possible and desirable, from other sources.

The subject of the search divides itself into two branches : (1) purchase of manuscripts for Government and publishing lists of them and (2) examining private collections and making their treasures known by the publication of catalogues. Taking a general survey of the whole work done in the Bombay Circle in connection with it we find that as regards purchase the success, as I shall show later on, has been very marked. Drs. Bühler, Kielhorn, Bhandarkar and Peterson sent their agents to different places for the purchase of manuscripts and they themselves paid visits to several places of longer or shorter duration. As a result a very large number of manuscripts has been purchased for Government and copies made of a number of such as the owners would not part with. Lists have been published of these accompanied by reports and some of the earliest of these reports and lists have been reprinted in Gough's Records of Ancient Sanskrit Literature. Not a few of the later reports, including those published by the Society, contain a great deal of very valuable literary and historical information gathered from a pretty close examination of the contents of a few of the manuscripts. Copious extracts from the manuscripts purchased also accompany these reports.

Not much has, however, been done as regards the publication of catalogues of manuscripts in private libraries, so far as the published results go. Dr. Bühler published four fascicles of a Catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscripts contained in the private libraries of Gujarat, Kathiavad, Kachchh, Sindh and Khandesh; and Dr. Kielhorn a Catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscripts existing in the Central Provinces and Fascicle I. of a Catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscripts

in the Southern Division of the Bombay Presidency. These do not give such abstracts and extracts as are given in Rajendralal's "Notices", for instance, and are therefore not of as much value as they would otherwise have been. Besides these, however, there have been published the extracts from manuscripts and the list of palm-leaf manuscripts in the Śāntināth Bhāndār at Cambay noticed above and three more catalogues of private libraries. A catalogue of manuscripts in the library of H. H. the Maharaj of Bikaner was published by Dr. Rajendralal before Rajputana was attached to the Bombay Circle. A similar catalogue of Sanskrit manuscripts in the library of H. H. the Maharaj of Alwar was published by Dr. Peterson and Part I. of lists of Sanskrit manuscripts in private libraries in the Bombay Presidency by Dr. Bhandarkar. These do not give merely the names of the works, the numbers of leaves, &c., but extracts also. In addition to these catalogues actually published there must have been, there are reasons to believe, some more lists and catalogues prepared, which have remained in manuscript, the scholars under whose superintendence they were prepared not having been able to publish them before their retirement. Dr. Bühler in one place refers to lists that were being made under his superintendence according to Dr. Rajendralal's scheme and in another place (Report of 8th June 1880) to a detailed report of his tour in Rajputana in 1873-74 which he had prepared for publication. This last would, I doubt not, have been as important as his Kaśmir report, and we cannot but regret the fact that he died without publishing it. Drs. Kielhorn and Bhandarkar too call two of the volumes they have published "Fascicle I." and "Part I.", clearly implying thereby that there were other fascicles and parts to follow.

A few remarks now as regards my own experience and future prospects of the search. In the history of the Bengal Asiatic Society, written by Dr. Rajendralal Mitra for the centenary of that Society, he in one place remarks that "Sanskrit manuscripts are not marketable articles, and the sanctity attached to them by the people of this country render them extremely difficult of access." That is as nearly true now as in the beginning of 1884. One instance will show how true it is now. When I started on my last tour, I first went to Indore and there learnt of a collection of manuscripts belonging to a Sardar there. He was out of Indore at the time and I went to his house to see if I could arrange with his agent to let me have a look at his manuscripts. On entering his compound I noticed that a great many things in the house had been spread out in the compound for exposing to the sun as a necessary preparation for the house being occupied again after the first severe epidemic of plague at Indore. Amongst the things spread out I noticed a

number of good old manuscripts, browned with age, of important works of Vedic, sacrificial and other literature. They were not the manuscripts I sought, but, as it proved to be the case, much more valuable, and were discovered thus very fortuitously. They belonged, I was told, to a Paurāṇika who had then recently died of plague and had been a dependent of the Sardar. On meeting the Sardar a few days after I told him that the manuscripts were of some importance and that he should see that they were properly cared for and preserved. I was surprised to hear from him, when he readily promised to do so, that up to the death of the Paurāṇika he never knew that he (the Paurāṇika) was possessed of such valuable manuscripts. The Paurāṇika had kept it a secret from him, though he must have known that his master took interest in Sanskrit literature.

But things are much better now than they were in the beginning of the search. There is in the library of Elphinstone College a small collection of manuscripts made for Government in 1866-68, a list of which was published by Dr. Bühler in a recent volume of the Journal of the German Oriental Society. The manuscripts are mostly copies made for Government and seem to have been made not always from good originals, but from such as were available, whether good or bad. The leaves of the originals were in some cases in great disorder or mixed up with leaves of other manuscripts and the copies represent exactly the state in which the originals were. With such manuscripts scholars engaged in the search had to content themselves at first.

In spite of all drawbacks, however, and in spite of what a writer in the pages of the Journal of the Sarvajanika Sabha about 22 years ago wrote as to the best manuscripts having gone to Germany, one result of the operations in connection with the search in the Bombay Circle has been the vast and splendid collection of manuscripts deposited in the Deccan College, Poona. So far back as February, 1878, the Government of India remarked with reference to it that "in Bombay the results were most satisfactory." And since then there have been large additions for so many years, including a number of old palm-leaf manuscripts. It would be no exaggeration to say that a critical edition of hardly a single Sanskrit work is published anywhere in the world at the present day without drawing upon the resources of this collection.

It is now not very easy to come across manuscripts of works not represented in the collection, and some years ago Dr. Bhandarkar consequently reported that twice he had to refund into the Government treasury an unused balance out of the annual grant at his disposal and made the suggestion that the regular grant for the search for manuscripts, which was much larger than at present, should be discontinued and that special grants should be made whenever the

Professors of Sanskrit at the two Government Colleges came across manuscripts worth buying. The suggestion was not carried out exactly in that way, but the grant was considerably reduced. Soon after occurred the death of Mr. Bhagvandas Kevaldas. He had been engaged as an agent for the purchase of manuscripts almost from the very beginning and had consequently a long experience of the business, knew what was represented already in the Government collection and what new works would therefore be worth purchasing, and could, with a trader's unerring instinct, scent new manuscripts. Not a little of the credit of the Government collection is due to him; and Dr. Peterson has, by the dedication of his Report for 1886-92, borne witness to the value of his assistance.

But there are yet not a few works mentioned and frequently quoted from in the available Sanskrit literature, which to scholars are

“ Still a hope, a love ;
Still longed for, never seen.”

Dr. Caland who has undertaken an edition of the Baudhāyana Śrauta Sūtra is in search of a manuscript of the complete work. Dr. Pischel has just reminded me of Guṇāḍhya's Bṛihatkathā in the Paiśāchī dialect, which was sanskritised almost simultaneously by two noted Kāśmirian poets of old, though there is hardly any necessity for one engaged in the search to be reminded of it. A few others are: Mānavadharmasūtra, Bhartrihari's Commentary on the Mahābhāshya, Rāvaṇa's Bhāshyas on the Ṛig and Yajur Vedas, a fresh manuscript of the Paippalāda Śākhā of the Atharva Veda, Bodhāyana's Vṛitti on the Vedānta Sūtras,—but I need not multiply the list. The hope of ever discovering these and others like them rests on the contents of all private libraries throughout the land being carefully examined by scholars. And even if they were not to be discovered, such an examination and the publication of catalogues as a result of it would be of the utmost use and value to scholars. But there is a great deal of unwillingness on the part of the owners to allow their manuscripts to see the light. Some of the causes of this unwillingness and a few instances of it I have referred to in my report to Government. First, there is the dislike to a stranger's eyes falling on what is treasured, howsoever carelessly, as a great possession. Secondly, there is a general distrust. In some way or other the manuscripts in a man's possession will not, it is thought, be allowed to remain with him long if once they come to the knowledge of others. And those, who know or have heard of the purchase of manuscripts by scholars either living in India or temporarily visiting it, allege their fear that the manuscripts would further find their way out of the country altogether. This last is not to be wondered at when the writer in the Sarvajanik Sabha's

Journal, referred to above, made the statement already noticed and a proposal was once actually made in 1868, when the search was first ordered, that the collections made for Government should be shipped to Europe. The owners cannot, of course, be expected to show that disinterested desire for the preservation of Sanskrit literature, which would make them feel that they had rather see the manuscripts in the possession of others and by them preserved carefully than that they should be lost and destroyed for want of due care on their own part.

Under these circumstances, there must spring up a close intimacy, such as would leave not a shadow of distrust, between the owners and the scholars who would examine their collections or some one on their behalf. That is a work of time and to that scholars must now devote themselves, if they wish to discover the works and manuscripts they so ardently long for, should they still be in existence, as some of them needs must be.

I shall conclude these remarks with a Praśasti from a manuscript I found in Gwalior. It is a manuscript of the medical work, called Vikramavilāsa, mentioned at page 8 of the report of my tour. I have had a temporary loan of the manuscript by the kindness of the Resident at Gwalior and of the Gwalior Durbar and have got a copy made of the praśasti.

Extracts from the MS. of Vikramavilāsa belonging to the State Collection at Gwalior.

Fol. 1 b—2b.

श्रीगणेशाय नमः ॥

श्रीया(मा)न् सर्वमुरासुरैरपि नतः कार्यादितः कार्यकृ-
द्विभारण्यदवाग्निरीशतनयः सर्वार्थसिद्धिप्रदः ॥
अन्तर्न्यस्ततमस्त्ववारणघटानिमूलनाकेसरी
ता(ना)गास्यो वितनोतु वः सुरवरः सत्कृत्य सन्मंगलम् ॥ १ ॥
येनाकारि निरंतरं रियु(पु)वधूने(ने)श्राम्बुसिक्ता मही
सर्वोध्यकपुरीव शासनवशा पाथोधिभयार्दया ॥
आवासः खलु संपदा प्रविलसद्दीरश्रिया सेवितो
भूपस्तोमरवंशभूषणमणि[ः] श्रो(श्री)देवम(व)र्माभवत् ॥ २ ॥
सुतानां ननु तस्येष्टमजनिष्ट चतुष्टयम् ॥ धर्मार्थकाममोक्षाणां चतुष्टयमिवापरम् ॥ ३ ॥
वीरसिंह इतिपूर्वजोभवत्कीर्त्यते तदनुजो हरसिंहः ॥
न(ना?)मतस्तदनुभूः शिववर्मा संपदा निधिरतोचलवर्मा ॥ ४ ॥
वीराणां धुरि कीर्त्तनीयचरितः को वीरसिंहं विना
प्रोदा(हा)मद्युतिदुर्नि[री]क्षचरितभेदप्रतापानलः॥
उदंडः परिभूय वारणघटावीरश्रियालिंगितो
यो वीरात्(न्) शिरसा विनैव समरे प्राणीनटत्कोटिशः ॥ ५ ॥

शीरसिंहे धराधीशे या नीतिः सा न कुत्रचित् ॥ यस्य द्वारमसेवंत गजव्याजेन भूधराः ॥ ६ ॥
 विदितसकलधर्मा प्रोल्लसच्चारुकर्मा विहितपुजनशर्मा सत्रयानीतदर्मा ॥
 प्रतिहतरिपुनर्मा विप्रसंदत्तभर्मा सग(म)जनि शिववर्मा ज्ञातपाण्डित्यमर्मा ॥ ७ ॥
 बलारिशिववर्माणौ पुरा धान्ना तुलाभूतौ ॥ पूर्वा लधुरगात्सर्गा(त्स्वर्ग)माललम्बे भुवं परः ॥ ८ ॥
 तल्लङ्गधारा धारा च स्वस्तटिन्या उभे वरे ॥ यत्र मन्ना न मज्जन्ति पुनः संसारवार(रि)धौ ॥ ९ ॥
 तस्मात्समुद्र(द्रा)दिव रत्नजातं भूया(पा)लरत्नं नृपरत्नपालः ॥
 संभूय शोभां महतीं ततान कुले समस्ते ननु तोमराणाम् ॥ १० ॥
 कीर्तिश्रीर्ननु रत्नपालनृपतेः सेयं समुज्जं(ज्जुं)भते
 यामालोक्य वितर्कयंति नितरां सत्कोविदाः सर्वतः ॥
 कर्पूरैः किमपूरि किं त्रिभुवनं श्रीखंडखंडै(ड)द्रवै-
 रालेपि प्रचलन्सुधांसु(शु)किरणैराच्छा(च्छा)दि किं सर्वतः ॥ ११ ॥
 सर्वासु दिक्षु प्रथितः पृथिव्यां श्रीरत्नपालप्रभुरेव दाता ॥
 इती[व] पूर्वा दिगसौ प्रभति गृहना (द्वा)ल्ययोगोलकमर्कविम्बम् ॥ १२ ॥
 यौ(यै)राराधि शिवा शिवानि ददती तेषां किमन्यः सुरः
 अया कल्पतरोरलंभि खलु यैस्तेषां किमन्यस्तरुः ॥
 यैरासादि लसन्सुवर्णशिखरी तेषां किमन्यो गिरि-
 रैरालोकि च रत्नपालनृपतिस्तेषां किमन्योनृपः ॥ १३ ॥
 कीर्तिश्च वैरिवासी(मा)श्च परे परे महोदधे [ः] ॥ येन दोर्हंडचंडेन सममेव निवासिताः ॥ १४ ॥
 वरं गणयते सुधीः सुरतरंगिनी(णी)वालुकाः ॥ पर(रं) कलयते वरं जलदवारिविदूनापि ॥
 भवंति मितिमध्यगाः सकलतारकाः कस्यचिन्न रत्नजगतीपतेर्गुणपयोधिंस्ख्याविधिः ॥ १५ ॥
 मुतो विक्रमसेनोभूत्तस्य विक्रमवारिधिः ॥ जवनीवदनाभोजवनीमुद्रासुधाकरः ॥ १६ ॥
 विक्रमस्य न तु विक्रमे समो रायरीशशकखंडने नृपः ॥
 योनययवनकामिनीमुखं रक्तमेव पुनरुत्तरुत्तताम् ॥ १७ ॥
 दानूणां तरणीन्दुवंशसरणिः सत्यं प्रसिद्धा खनिर्हाता विक्रमसेनभूपसदृशः कश्चिन्न वृष्टः पुनः ॥
 यष्टकैः परितक्ष्य कांचनमथैदा(दौ)रिद्यमुद्रां द्र(दृ)ढं भूपालीकुरु[ते]थिनस्तदनिशं जागर्ति भूमं-
 डले ॥ १८ ॥
 चिंतामणिश्चितितमेव दत्ते संकल्पितं कल्पतरुर्ददाति ॥
 अर्चितिताकल्पितदानदक्षः सविक्रमो विक्रमसेनभूपः ॥ १९ ॥
 विलोक्य नेत्रविस्तारं यदरातिमृगीदृशां ॥
 काननात्तद्गृहान्याति मार्गमीय्यो(र्व्यो)कदधि(धि) तं ॥ २० ॥
 क्रोदं कलयति के न जगतीनाथा विना[-]स्पदास्तेषां विक्रमसेनभूपतिलको धुर्यः परं गणयते ॥
 येनारातिवभूमुखेषु नितरां नेत्राभ्रपूर्णेवहो दत्ता कज्जलकालिमा खलु पुनर्नो नेत्रयोः कज्जलं ॥२१ ॥
 गदनिपीडितलोकविलोकनं ननु विधाय सदा करुणाकरः ॥
 तदुपसंहृतितंत्रमचीकरत्स खलु विक्रमसेनमहीपतिः ॥ २२ ॥
 दृष्ट्वा मुहुश्चरकमुभुतवाग्भटादीन् हारीतभेडकलिकाखरनाददृदं ॥
 विश्वोपकारकरणैकपरायणोयं ग्रंथं व्यधत्त ननु विक्रमसेनभूपः ॥ २३ ॥

Fol. 230 a—b.

श्री

विक्रमसेनविभुना विभुनायकेन नानामुनिप्रकटितानि [~-~] वीक्ष्य
 ग्रंथस्तु विक्रमविलास इति प्रसिद्धो विस्तारितो जगति कीर्तिविकाशनाय ॥ १ ॥
 अन्दे ष[र]महपाथोभिनादयुक्ताकसंज्ञिते । ज्येष्ठे(ष्ठे)शुक्लप्रयोदश्यां ग्रथ (ग्रंथः) संपूर्णतां गतः
 आयुर्वेदविधानविद्विष्वर(रव)नौ भूरिप्रवन्धा : कृताः
 यद्यप्येष तथापि का[पि ?] सराणिभिन्नेयमाभासते ।
 ग्रंथे विक्रमसेनदेवविहिते यं वीक्ष्य वैद्यप्रियं
 प्रष्टुं नान्यनिबंधनं कलयते विद्वान् मिष क्पुङ्गवः ॥ ३ ॥
 यावद्ब्रामकथामुषा कथयते विद्वज्जनानां श्रुती [ः] यावन्निरर्जरनिर्झरिण्यपि जगत्पोष्यते पावनी ।
 सूर्याचं(चं)ह्रमसौ च यावदखिलं ध्नंतौ तमो राजतस्तावाद्दिक्रमसेनदेवजगतीजानिश्विरं जीवतु ॥४॥
 जीमूता[ः]मुखकारि वारि परितो मुंचंतु पृथ्वी सदा धान्यानां जनिमादधातु जगतीनाथो भुवं रक्षतु ।
 संतः संतु सुखैकसेवनपरा धर्मैः परं कर्द्धतां भूक्षेपैः परकार्यपाटनपटुः प्राप्नोतु नाशं खलः ॥ ५ ॥
 भूपाला जगती[ती] पातु प्रजा नंदंतु सर्वतः वेदाभ्यासरता विप्रा दुःसंतो धेनवः शुभाः ॥ ६ ॥
 इति विक्रमविलासः ग्रंथ[ः] समाप्तः ॥ ॥ शुभमस्तु लेखकपाठकयोः ॥ संवत् १८७३का चैत्र
 कृष्ण २ भौमवासरात्रितायां लिखितोयं ब्राह्मणरामलाल शुभं भूयात् ।

It will be seen that the genealogy given in the above extracts begins with Devavarman of the Tomara dynasty. He had four sons :— Virasimha, Harasimha, Śivavarman and Achalavarman. Virasimha became king. Śivavarman's bravery and learning are mentioned. But he is not mentioned as having ruled. His son was king Ratnapāla and Ratnapāla's son was king Vikramasena, the author of the present work. The work was completed in (Samvat) 1496 or 1440 A.D.

Virasimha is of course the king who founded the Tomara dynasty of Gwalior, the same to whom the Vīrasimhāvaloka and other works are attributed. Deo Brahma or Brahmadeo also (Cunningham's Archæological Survey of India, Vol. II, p. 302) must be the same as Devavarman (see Dr. Bhandarkar's Report for 1883-84, p. 86). Vikramasena was thus the grandson of a brother of Vīrasimha. Both he and his father were kings, but no other record of them seems to have turned up as yet.